

The Network InnoChain

edited by:
IAAC - Institute for Advanced
Architecture of Catalonia

A RESEARCH NETWORK SUPPORTED BY:
European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

ORGANISERS: InnoChain ETN network

PROJECT ACRONYM: InnoChain

START DATE OF THE PROJECT: 01/09/2015

DURATION OF THE PROJECT: 48 months

ORGANISATION NAME OF LEAD BENEFICIARY FOR THIS TASK: IAAC

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INNOCHAIN - CHALLENGING THE TRADITIONAL THINKING OF DESIGN

The InnoChain ETN network is a shared research training environment examining how advances in digital design tools challenge building culture enabling sustainable, informed and materially smart design solutions. The network aims to train a new generation of interdisciplinary researchers with a strong industry focus that can effect real changes in the way we think, design and build our physical environment.

PROGRAMME

The programme investigates the extended digital chain as a particular opportunity for interdisciplinary design collaboration. Challenging the traditional thinking of design as a linear process of incremental refinement, InnoChain identifies three axes of design innovation potential communication, simulation and materialisation appearing as distributed and interdisciplinary activities across the design chain. Situating feedback between design processes as a key concern for developing holistic and integrated design methods, the network will develop new interdisciplinary design methods that integrate advanced simulation and interface with material

fabrication.

With a strong inter-sector focus, InnoChain connects “research in practice” with “research in academia”. Assembling 6 internationally recognised academic research environments leading research into computational design in architecture and engineering and 14 innovation pioneering industry partners from architecture, engineering, design software development and fabrication, the programme will establish a shared training platform for 15 early stage researchers. The network creates a structured training programme focussed on supervision of individual research projects, an inter-sector secondment programme as well as collective research events including workshop-seminars, colloquia, summer school and research courses that provide a unique opportunity for young researchers to obtain new knowledge and skills positioning them between strong innovative research practice and influential industrial impact.

Challenging the traditional thinking of design as a linear process of incremental refinement

The network is funded by the European Union’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020, under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Innovative Training Network scheme.

Academic Partners

CITA — BSA — ITKE — IOA

— KTH — IAAC

The research network assembles a highly cross disciplinary team of experienced researchers drawn from architecture (CITA/KADK (coordinator), Bartlett School of Architecture, Institut d'Arquitectura Avançada de Catalunya and Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan) and engineering (Universität Stuttgart/ITKE and Universität für Angewandte Kunst Vienna/IOA) and leading industry partners (Foster + Partners, White Arkitekter, BIG, HENN, ROK, Cloud 9, Buro Happold, str.ucture, designtoproduction, Smith Innovation, Blumer-Lehmann, S-Form, Factum Arte Desarrollos Digitales and McNeel Europe).

CITA

CENTRE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY
AND ARCHITECTURE, THE ROYAL DANISH
ACADEMY OF FINE ARTS, SCHOOLS OF
ARCHITECTURE, DESIGN AND CONSERVATION

CITA focuses on IT as a tool for design, production and communication within key research areas: Digital Formations: new parametric design tools and their physical counterpart: Building Information Modelling, Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided Manufacture. Behaving Architectures: new programmable materials including nanotechnologies and interactive textiles. Interface Ecologies: real-time modelling, interface design and intelligent programming.

CITA has a strong track record in initiating and running research projects and networks with international partnerships. In 2011 CITA completed the nationally funded research network Digital Crafting cementing many of InnoChain's industrial and academic collaborations. In 2012 Mette Ramsgard Thomsen was awarded the Danish Council for Independent Research Sapere Aude Advanced Research Grant for elite research at top research level.

CITA has a strong international reputation and is a central part of the research community on computation and architecture. In 2011 CITA hosted the core research conference Smart Geometry and in 2015 we will host another central conference

Design Modelling Symposium. CITA's research has a strong focus on industry collaboration both nationally and internationally through an established programme of industrial PhDs, consultancy, training and research collaboration.

STAFF

Professor Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen, Associate Professor Martin Tamke, Associate Professor Phil Ayres.

ESRS

Tom Svilans - ESR02, Paul Poinet - ESR06, Kasper Ax - ESR14.

BSA

**THE BARTLETT SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON**

University College London is ranked fourth in the QS World University rankings and is the highest ranked among the Architecture and Built Environment submissions in the UK 2008 Research Assessment Exercise (RAE), with the highest percentage of world-leading 4* staff outputs in the field. BSA has the UK's largest pool of PhD candidates in the field of the Built environment at more than 150 enrolled. The School of Architecture, is also the UK's leading teaching academy in the field and currently holds all RIBA international medals for best student projects at BSc, Masters, and PhD, in design and dissertation. The School employs over 130 staff including architects, researchers, technical specialists, designers, artists, historians, and engineers. In recent years the School has invested heavily in emerging digital technologies (£3-4m) and firstly set up the Digital Manufacturing Centre (2008), which has more recently been subsumed into B-made (The Bartlett Manufacturing and Design Exchange in 2013). In conjunction with the Schools new suite of Post Professional Masters programmes known as B-Pro, B-MADE operates laboratory and workshop facilities at an industrial scale. B-made also

integrates with UCL's Engineering Faculty and its substantial strength in related research and resources. Elsewhere in the Faculty, the Bartlett includes several world renowned research groups such as SPACE, The Energy Institute, CASA, etc, each of whom have a record of securing and delivering large scale funded research packages for the UK in the order of 10's of £m's.

The School has a strong track record and is highly active in a diverse range of subjects including advanced computation for Spatial Analysis, Environments, Design, and Fabrication, as well as material behaviours, craft, and innovative manufacturing methods. The School is in an unrivalled position in the UK to centre research for the built environment across such a broad range of work in strength, thus providing it with the unique facility to develop, theorise, and apply its findings. Many established research networks were established at the Bartlett including Space Syntax 1995, Smart Geometry in 2002, FABRICATE 2011, as well as hosting networks established elsewhere such as Design Computing and Cognition (2014) and Advanced Architectural Geometry (2014).

STAFF

Professor, Director of School Bob Sheil, Dr. Sean Hanna, Professor Stephen Gage, Professor Mario Carpo, and Visiting Professor Robert Aish.

ESRS

Dimitrie Stefanescu - ESR05, Giulio Brugnaro - ESR10, Arthur Prior - ESR13.

ITKE

**INSTITUTE OF BUILDING STRUCTURES AND
STRUCTURAL DESIGN, UNIVERSITY OF
STUTT GART**

The Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (ITKE) based at the University of Stuttgart is a leading institute in the research of innovative structural systems and high performance materials.

The Institute is composed by an interdisciplinary group of 14 researchers working in a highly synergic environment.

ITKE engages in research and teaching with new materials and efficient structures for architecture. The Institute is highly interdisciplinary, employing engineers and architects, bridging the gap between architecture and structural engineering. The focus of research activities is on building with polymers, textiles and glass. Issues of design and material implementation and the planning and optimization process are central to the Institute's research.

STAFF

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Jan Knippers.

ESRS

Evy Laura Maurice Slabbinck - ESR01, James Solly - ESR08, Saman Saffarian - ESR12.

IoA

INSTITUTE OF ARCHITECTURE (IOA), THE
UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED ARTS VIENNA

The goal of the Institute of Architecture at the University of Applied Arts Vienna and of its Dean Klaus Bollinger is to teach architecture as an all-inclusive thought process that puts the future architect in the position to define architecture as a three-dimensional expression of culture. To achieve this, the three design studios of Kazuyo Sejima, Greg Lynn and Hani Rashid closely work together with specialists in the departments of technology, theory and editing within our institute, as well as with specialists from reputable external organizations.

This potential for interaction is realized in closely networked teams that are kept comparatively small to facilitate the transfer of knowledge. In computerlabs and state-of-the-art model shops, the latest technologies are tested in theory and practice. The continuous necessity of re-defining architecture both in theoretical and practical terms should be the main focus of teaching.

STAFF

o.Univ.-Professor Dipl.Ing. Dr.techn. Klaus Bollinger, Dipl.Ing.

Dr.techn. Clemens Preisinger and Sen.Art. Dipl.arch. MArch. Anja Jonkhans.

ESRS

Zeynep Aksöz - ESR04, Christoph Hermann - ESR07

KTH

**SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE – ARCHITECTURAL
TECHNOLOGY**

The KTH School of Architecture is a platform for learning, researching and practicing the role and agency of architecture in its technological, cultural and socio-political context. The Architectural Technology research environment conceives computational design and digital technologies as means to tackle complexity within urban, architectural, structural and material scale. A strong focus is put on interdisciplinarity of architects and engineers with key figures of the world leading structural design practices (such as AKT and Bollinger + Grohman) contributing to research and teaching.

KTH School of Architecture is a key partner in two strong research environments in architectural theory and method: "Architecture in the Making" and "Architecture in Effect". The national initiative links the four schools of architecture in Sweden. The Architectural Technology research environment currently runs a 3-year research project on a novel convergence of computational design, digital fabrication, concrete and innovative formwork and contributes to the research on designing an Energy Efficient Campus in Albano.

The PhD Programme in Architecture encompasses specializations in Architectural Design, Architectural Technology, Critical Theory, Theory and History, and Urban Design. Since 2012, the School additionally participates in the Swedish national research school, ResArc, expanding the range of high quality courses available for PhD students.

STAFF

Assistant Professor Oliver Tessmann, Professor Johan Silfwerbrand and Professor Ulrika Karlsson.

ESRS

Vasily Sitnikov - ESR09, Helena Westerlind - ESR11

IAAC

INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED ARCHITECTURE OF
CATALONIA, UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE
CATALUNYA

The Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia is an international centre for Education Fabrication and Research dedicated to the development of architecture capable of meeting the worldwide challenges in constructing 21st century habitability.

Based in the 22@ district of Barcelona, one of the world's capitals of architecture and urbanism, IAAC is a platform for the exchange of knowledge with researchers, faculty and students from over 60 countries. Every year IAAC selects 100 new students from all over the world that gather at IAAC and give life to this significant laboratory for experimentation in order to envision the dwellings and the cities of our time, as well as their future.

IAAC is Education, with the Master in Advanced Architecture and the Master in City & Technology giving the next generation of architects the space to imagine, test and shape the future of cities, architecture and technology.

IAAC is Fabrication, with the Fab Lab Barcelona, the most advanced digital production laboratory in Southern Europe,

a laboratory where you can build almost everything, that recently hosted Fab10, the 10th annual worldwide Fab Lab conference.

IAAC is Research, with Valldaura Labs, a self-sufficient research centre located in the Collserola Metropolitan park where a series of laboratories are implemented for the production and testing of Energy, Food and Things.

And IAAC is also Barcelona, the European Capital for Innovation (2014), the city that aims to be a self-sufficient city, a fab-lab city, a smarter city. Thanks to its innovative visions, IAAC is strategically aligned to the new urban policies of the city, developed in close collaboration and mutual inspiration between the two entities.

STAFF

Professor Manuel Gausa, Professor Eduard Bru, Associate Professor Areti Markopoulou, Dr. Mathilde Marengo, and Dr Chiara Farinea.

ESRS

Angelos Chronis - ESR03, Stephanie Chaltiel - ESR15.

Academic Partners
Foster + Partners – White
– BIG – HENN – ROK
Cloud9 – Buro Happold –
str.ucture – D2P – Smith
– Blumer Lehmann – Sform –
Factum Arte – McNeel

The network aims to train a new generation of interdisciplinary researchers with a strong industry focus that can effect real changes in the way we think, design and build our physical environment. The InnoChain network counts on the partnership of leading industry partners (Foster + Partners, White Arkitekter, BIG, HENN, ROK, Cloud 9, Buro Happold, str.ucture, designtoproduction, Smith Innovation, Blumer-Lehmann, S-Form, Factum Arte Desarrollos Digitales and McNeel Europe) allowing the intergration and exchange between academia and the industry.

Foster + Partners

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

Foster + Partners understands that the best design comes from a completely integrated approach from conception to completion. We have a strong creative team, in which structural and environmental engineers work alongside the architects from the beginning of the design process. By doing so, we believe that they can learn from one another and combine their knowledge to devise wholly integrated design solutions. The design teams are supported by numerous in-house disciplines, ensuring that we have the knowledge base to create buildings that are environmentally sustainable and uplifting to use.

STAFF

Xavier De Kestelier - joint head of Foster + Partners' Specialist Modelling Group (SMG).

ESRS

Angelos Chronis - ESR03, James Solly - ESR08, Arthur Prior - ESR13.

white

Good architecture makes people grow. For us, houses, landscapes, rooms, furniture, fixtures, streets and districts provide the framework for a sustainable lifestyle. Driven by curiosity, we explore what is possible but seldom imagined. Together, we find sustainable answers, both for today and tomorrow.

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Innovation is at the core of our practice and culture and we invest heavily in research, development and training. We have built up our research capabilities over 6 decades to support our projects with the latest developments, needs and opportunities, trends and behaviours. A network operates throughout the practice to share experiences and lessons learned.

Our inquisitive culture forms the backbone of everything we do. Driven by a desire to explore the unknown and find new solutions we initiate research projects as well as in partnership with academic and commercial partners, locally and globally.

STAFF

Jonas Runberger - Director of Dsearch.

ESRS

Tom Svilans - ESR02, Helena Westerlind - ESR11.

BIG

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

BIG is a Copenhagen and New York based group of architects, designers, builders and thinkers operating within the fields of architecture, urbanism, research and development. The office is currently involved in a large number of projects throughout Europe, North America, Asia and the Middle East. BIG's architecture emerges out of a careful analysis of how contemporary life constantly evolves and changes. Not least due to the influence from multicultural exchange, global economical flows and communication technologies that all together require new ways of architectural and urban organization. We believe that in order to deal with today's challenges, architecture can profitably move into a field that has been largely unexplored. A pragmatic utopian architecture that steers clear of the petrifying pragmatism of boring boxes and the naïve utopian ideas of digital formalism. Like a form of programmatic alchemy we create architecture by mixing conventional ingredients such as living, leisure, working, parking and shopping. By hitting the fertile overlap between pragmatic and utopia, we architects once again find the freedom to change the surface of our planet, to better fit contemporary life forms.

STAFF

Dr Tore Banke - Computational Design Specialist.

ESRS

Evy Laura Maurice Slabbinck - ESR01, Zeynep Aksöz - ESR04, Giulio Brugnaro - ESR10.

**HE
NN**

HENN is an international architecture office with offices in Munich, Berlin and Beijing and 65 years of expertise in the fields of culture and office buildings, teaching and research as well as development, production and masterplanning.

The office is led by Gunter Henn and fourteen partners. 350 employees – architects, designers, planners and engineers – from 25 countries are able to draw upon a wealth of knowledge collected over three generations of building experience in addition to a worldwide network of partners and experts in a variety of disciplines.

This continuity, coupled with progressive design approaches and methods and interdisciplinary research projects, forms the basis for a continual examination of current issues and for a consistent design philosophy. Forms and spaces are no mere objective, they are developed from the processes, demands and cultural contexts of each project. As a general contractor we are able to satisfy this principle at every stage of project planning and implementation.

STAFF

Martin Henn - Design Director, Moritz Fleischmann - Research Consultant.

ESRS

Dimitrie Stefanescu - ESR05.

ROK

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

ROK is a practice for architecture and research located in Zurich. Architecture for us is the creative translation of complex requirements of our clients into individual and unique designs solutions. The common ground of our work, from small-scale interiors to large span structures, is our unique expertise in the field of innovative construction, automated fabrication and computer-based planning. We combine this knowledge with a deep understanding of craftsmanship in order to deliver outstanding and efficient architecture. Efficiency means to conceive designs that are sustainable and appropriate for the material involved, as well as executing a project economically and in due time.

STAFF

Michael Knauß - Founding Partner, Silvan Oesterle - Founding Partner.

ESRS

Giulio Brugnaro - ESR10, Stephanie Chaltiel - ESR15.

clouds
Enric Ruiz-Geli

www.ruiz-geli.com
Barcelona, Spain

Enric Ruiz-Geli founded Cloud 9 in 1997. The study is defined as: "Enric Ruiz-Geli and his interdisciplinary architectural team Cloud 9, located in Barcelona, working at the interface between architecture and art, digital processes and the development of technological materials. His multifaceted projects include scenarios and buildings, and industrial facilities, and are made with various partners. Cloud 9 is committed to the use of new technological developments and the performative dimension of architecture, creating smart structures mimicking nature."

STAFF

Enric Ruiz Geli - Founding Partner, Mireia Luzzaraga - Project Manager.

ESRS

Christoph Hermann - ESR07, Stephanie Chaltiel - ESR15.

BUROHAPPOLD
ENGINEERING

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

www.burohappold.com
Bath, London, Copenhagen, more.

BuroHappold Engineering is an international, integrated engineering consultancy operating in 23 locations worldwide, with over 50 partners and 1,500 staff including some of the world's leading consulting engineers. For 40 years we've been building our reputation for delivering creative, value led building and city solutions for an ever changing world.

Use our Enginuity tool to inform your choices and show the range of integrated specialisms that could be employed to achieve your project vision. Simply select your project scale, then your area of interest.

Next choose the Enginuity 'accent' you would like for your project. We don't expect it to provide a definitive answer, but it gives enough information to start the conversation. Have a play, then talk to us about how we could begin the journey together to make your vision viable.

STAFF

Dr Al Fisher - Associate.

ESRS

Paul Poinet - ESR06, Vasily Sitnikov - ESR09, Arthur Prior - ESR13.

structure

LIGHTWEIGHT DESIGN. MADE IN STUTTGART

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

str.ucture is an engineering company committed to the development of innovative lightweight solutions. We are experts on specialised methods of calculation and simulation. Our strength lies in turning complex analyses into solutions for challenging design tasks. str.ucture is a company of consulting engineers registered with the Baden-Württemberg Chamber of Engineers.

str.ucture stands for a design process where structures or components optimally fulfill their mission with minimal materials usage and minimal manufacturing effort. Perfectly shaped design is clear, simple, and logical. It is the aim to achieve more with less. Innovative thinking and solution-oriented methods of the Stuttgart school have strongly influenced our development.

Our qualification is due to internationally renowned engineers such as Fritz Leonhardt, Frei Otto, Jörg Schlaich, Jan Knippers and Werner Sobek. Together with excellent teachers like Jürgen Bradatsch, Eberhard Haug and Kai Uwe Bletzinger they served as inspiring examples and convince us that the secret of lightweight design lies in constantly expanding the limits of what is achievable.

STAFF

Dr. Julian Lienhard - Managing Director.

ESRS

Zeynep Asköz - ESR04, Saman Saffarian - ESR12.

design
to
production

Design-to-Production was founded in 2007 by Fabian Scheurer and Arnold Walz. Together, the IT specialist and the architect soon realised that each of them was active, one at the beginning and one at the end, in the same digital process chain, but that, between these extremes, many links were missing. So they became the first to offer Production-oriented data modelling as an independent service. In 2009 Hanno Stehling joined the team, and then, two years later, Johannes Kuhnen.

Providing the missing link: As pioneers of building information modeling, we close the process chain that links a construction idea to its fabrication.

For years we have enabled non-standard projects of high complexity to take flight and have supported architects, planning experts and manufacturers in reaching new heights of efficiency, safety and quality.

Design-to-Production – we master complexity.

STAFF

Fabian Scheurer - Managing Partner, Digital Planning and Consultancy.

ESRS

Paul Poinet - ESR06, Kasper Ax - ESR14.

Smith

Innovating construction

Smith is an external R&D agency for the building industry. Smith is a Danish consultancy firm working solely within the building industry. Our goal is to unleash the innovation potential of this major industry – to the benefit of companies, customers and society.

Smith is deeply rooted in an academic background within economics and social science. This enables us to address often neglected perspectives in a product- and project-oriented industry. We believe this cross-functional approach is the key to success regardless of whether we are enabling firms to develop new services or providing policy recommendations for governmental institutions.

Smith has a strong network within the Danish building sector. For 20 years, we have worked for, and in, all parts of the value chain ranging from public and private construction clients, architectural and engineering firms, contractors, material producers as well as in related funding and research agencies.

STAFF

Natalie Mossin - Associate Partner.

**Blumer
Lehmann**

The fascinating world of wood

Since the founding of the Leonhard Lehmann sawmill in 1875, the heart of every venture has been the fascinating world of wood. We have seized opportunities, integrated new areas of business and continually improved and expanded our areas of expertise. In the process, we have made our companies at Erlenhof what they are today, with more than 200 employees. Our companies use the raw material in its entirety and always with sustainability in mind: after it has been used for construction, the waste timber is used as an energy source.

Consulting, components, preforms, prototyping
Lehmann Timber Code AG is a center of excellence for CNC machining and digital production. Our specialists for the construction of components and preforms and produce with digital high-end processes freely shaped, geometrically complex structures.

STAFF

Kai Strehlke - Head of Department, Martin Antemann - CEO of Lehmann Timber Code AG.

ESRS

Tom Svilans - ESR02, Christoph Hermann - ESR07, Kasper Ax - ESR14.

S-form was founded in 1988.

The manufacturing of GFRP and CFRP parts for highest mechanic and dynamic demands is the companies focus including the conception and design of products, the fabrication of moulds, models and prototypes in automotive and racing. The company is aiming at high value for clients and innovative solutions, developed in close collaborations.

More than 25 years in a competitive market provided S-Form with know how and ability to innovate in construction and fabrication processes. The company provides high value for money, flexibility and punctuality and resource- and environmentally friendly production processes.

STAFF

Werner Schaeberle - Company Owner.

ESRS

James Solly - ESR08, Saman Saffarian - ESR12.

FACTUM **arte**

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INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS

Based in Madrid, London and Milan, Factum Arte consists of a team of artists, technicians and conservators dedicated to digital mediation – both in the production of works for contemporary artists and in the production of facsimiles as part of a coherent approach to preservation and dissemination. Bespoke equipment has been designed and software has been written to obtain optimum results in both recording and outputting digital information. Factum Arte's non-contact methodologies are having a growing impact on the world of conservation and are defining the role facsimiles play in the protection of our cultural heritage.

The role of facsimiles and issues of objectivity are central to the work. The aim of most projects carried out in Factum Arte's workshops is to demonstrate how new technologies can assume a central role in the preventative conservation of heritage sites and can change attitudes towards the use of digital data (both virtual and physical) in the management and protection of cultural heritage.

STAFF

Adam Lowe - Founder.

ESRS

Helena Westerlind - ESR11.

.Suni.es
om
.accurender.com
www.latiendadelcad.com
www.bongo3d.com
www.pipe2d.com
www.concept3d.com
www.flaming3d.com
www.bubbles3d.com
www.pang3d.com
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Founded in 1980, Robert McNeel & Associates is a privately-held, employee-owned software development company with sales and support offices and affiliates in Seattle, Boston, Miami, Barcelona, Rome, Turku, Tokyo, Taipei, Seoul, Kuala Lumpur, Shenzhen and Shanghai with more than 500 resellers, distributors, OEMs, and training centers around the world.

Founded in 1995, McNeel Europe is the EMEA (Europe, Middle East and Africa) division of the company, responsible for sales, marketing, training, support, and localization of all McNeel products in that region. McNeel Europe also has a Development team and manages food4Rhino, the Rhino and Grasshopper apps repository.

STAFF

Carlos Pérez Albà - Technical Support & Training, Luis Fraguada - Research Director, Verena Vogler - Technical Support & Training.

ESRS

Evy Laura Maurice Slabbinck - ESR01, Angelos Chronis - ESR03.

The Research

Communicating design

Current methods for communicating domain specific knowledge in building practice assume disciplinary separation and discretisation of design control. State of the art research questions these professional boundaries by creating shared methods that integrate design and simulation. However, these methods either remain data heavy and therefore unintuitive and contrary to design creativity or borrow methods from unrelated fields such as film industry. These ad hoc methods remain highly experimental and unverified.

The topic is tackled in the innochain Work package 3, which will examine innovative links between structural simulation, material and design.

The Workpackage is lead by the Institute of Building Structures and Structural Design (ITKE)

INTEGRATING ISOGEOMETRIC ANALYSIS

in the design of bending-active-hybrid structures

EVY LAURA MAURICE SLABBINCK

ESR NUMBER: ESR01

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG & McNeel

INSTITUTE: ITKE

The research conducts on the one hand the integration of Isogeometric Analysis into architecture and design, and on the other hand the extension and exploration of the bending-active-hybrid design space.

Isogeometric Analysis (IGA) is an emerging technology driven by the present gap between the simulation of structural analysis and design software. This newly developed computational method is a new approach to Finite Element Method, taking non-approximated geometry into consideration by using conventional NURBS-based CAD models (Figure 01). The isogeometric concept of using the same basis for geometry and analysis enables a higher level of communication and integration. The research aims at the integration of Isogeometric Analysis into today's CAD packages and an exploration of its potential for architectural design culture. Bending-active tensile structures introduce a new integrative solution into the field of lightweight architecture. This combination of bending-active elements with a tensile element generates challenges for designers due to the complexity in the necessary integrated form-finding and analysis simulations, as well as the high level of detail required in fabrication and erection of these

Design mode: Dynamic Relaxation on Static Topological Spaces
 Tool: Custom-Built Grasshopper Plugin (ElasticSpaceGH / Seiichi Suzuki Erazo)

Assembly of the system

Relaxation

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Design mode: Dynamic Relaxation on Mutable Topological Spaces
 Tool: Custom-Built Java Application (ElasticSpace / Seiichi Suzuki Erazo)

Fixing connectivity of elastic rods

Adding membrane topology

Final Model

01_a PURE BENDING + TENSION

01_b TORSION + TENSION

01_c TORSION + COMPRESSION

PHYSICAL SPACE

CONTROL NET

PHYSICAL MESH

PARAMETER SPACE

INDEX SPACE

PARENT ELEMENT

form-active structures. The currently-built structures only make use of circular sections and avoid fully-symmetrical sections. Attaching a membrane structure to a circular cross-section is far less intricate and time-consuming as pockets or sleeves in the membrane perform generally very well for connecting an edge of a membrane to a support system. Additionally there is a reduction in

simulation complexity for fully-symmetric sections. The use of pure tensile components with the bending-active elements reduce the geometrical possibilities due to the reciprocal equilibrium between both elements (Figure 02). An extension of pure tensile forces to axial forces will expand the design space and give more freedom to the designer to tailor the geometry and generate new tectonic possibilities in architecture (Figure 03). The use of fibres and fibre reinforced textiles could represent a possible solution.

The connection of the membrane to the bending-active elements, the bi-axial pre-stress, the complexity in simulation and fabrication, and the relative low ability to take forces is a prominent problem and has limited the currently-built structures. Isogeometric Analysis goes beyond the advantages of Finite Element analysis as it uses a continuous geometry and avoids locking in shell structures and performs well for contact problems. The high deformation and the fibre-fibre interaction is hard to simulate in standard Finite Element software and poses an ideal case study for research in Isogeometric Analysis.

Since the commencement of the research, time have been divided over two diverse but connecting subjects: theoretical literature study concerning IGA and research into digital simulation and software development for bending-active tensile structures (Figure 04).

The project is engaged with two well-known industry partners in the field of architecture and structural engineering: BIG (architectural office) and McNeel Europe (software development company). The collaboration with McNeel Europe focuses on the integration of IGA in commercial software. The collaboration with BIG at the moment is still in discussion but will be in a later stage and will cover more the field of research-by-design.

INTEGRATING MATERIAL PERFORMANCE in glue-laminated timber assemblies

TOM SVILANS

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THE RESEARCH

ESR NUMBER: ESR02

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Blumer Lehmann & White

INSTITUTE: CITA

This PhD project investigates the potential of free-form glue-laminated timber in architectural design and fabrication. The project addresses three distinct but overlapping themes: the production and communication of knowledge across design, development, and fabrication networks; the integration of material performance as a design driver; and the application of digital simulation and acquisition tools in glue-laminated timber design and production pipelines. Developments in material sciences, digital design and development tools, and fabrication techniques have added an unprecedented amount of complexity to the design and production of buildings. This novel condition necessitates alternate ways of conceptualizing and managing the design-production process and has made obvious the need for integration across disciplines, specializations, and scales. The ability to simulate complex behavior in materials such as timber has opened the door to materially-driven design solutions and new structural morphologies.

Glue-laminated timber represents a particular opportunity for architectural construction because it is materially sustainable, structurally scalable, and is easier to shape and process compared

to other forms of construction. Beyond these immediate considerations, timber has a long and rich history, both in its use and its cultural and aesthetic perception. The glulam also presents wide formal possibilities and a material richness that can be more difficult to achieve with other construction materials such as steel or concrete.

While being primarily composed of one of the oldest building materials - wood - glulam technology has only been made possible by the relatively recent (early 20th century) developments in structural adhesives. Combined with the resurgence of a general discourse about sustainability in contemporary AEC industries and the ubiquitous application of digital computation to fabrication methods, glue-laminated timber has come to the forefront of current architectural materials and building systems. This new context allows this material to be examined in much finer detail than before. The ability to simulate and compute complex behaviors and material properties creates the opportunity to use laminated timber more strategically both in terms of architectural performance and material usage. Specifically, the effect of fibre orientation within glue-laminated timber assemblies presents both a computational challenge and an opportunity to capitalize on the various material behaviors that it provokes. This PhD project looks at what the ramifications of this ability are both for industrial fabrication and within commercial architectural practice.

The project is a collaboration with two high-profile industrial partners, each with a world-class portfolio and with wide expertise in their respective fields: White arkitekter AB, a multi-disciplinary architectural practice based in Gothenburg and Stockholm, Sweden; and Timber Code AG, an industrial timber fabricator in Gossau,

Switzerland. At White, Dsearch is a research unit that looks at how computation and digital workflows are integrated into large-scale architectural practice, and how new technologies can be deployed alongside and within other, more traditional modes of working. Timber Code specializes in the application of digital technologies and computation to large-scale engineered timber fabrication, an expertise which it has extensively demonstrated through work on many internationally-acclaimed timber projects. This choice of industrial partners allows the project to be contextualized between contrasting realms of practice and production.

This PhD unfolds primarily through a research-by-design method based on experiments in the form of speculative probes, prototypes, and demonstrators. The method of inquiry is parallel strands of physical prototyping and information modeling, drawing on the expertise of the industrial partners and the testing of

workflows through workshops, case-studies, and other forms of teaching. As the research is concerned with two distinct scales and arenas - design computation in a multi-disciplinary commercial architectural context, and material-technology integration in a hands-on fabrication and delivery context - the method will move between the experimentation, design, and testing of the material prototypes, and more abstract information models that will transfer key data to a more flexible and accessible design scenario. The topic will be investigated through a cross-disciplinary and trans-scalar integration of different classes of parameters - exposing specific fabrication parameters within a generalized design context and vice versa.

INTEGRATING BUILDING PHYSICS FOR PERFORMANCE CONTROL

ANGELOS CHRONIS

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THE RESEARCH

ESR NUMBER: ESR03

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Foster + Partners & McNeel

INSTITUTE: IAAC

The integration of building performance feedback in the design process is increasingly considered as a key aspect of the decision support framework that can drive current high performance architecture, from early conception to fabrication. The computational paradigm shift that leads the research in design methodology has been closely followed by an abundant development and integration of performance analysis methods and tools that aim to support the performance aims of these novel form-found and optimized architectures.

Despite this increasing significance of building performance simulation (BPS) tools and their consequent continuous development and integration in CAAD software, it is generally acknowledged (Clarke & Hensen 2015) that currently available BPS tools are substantially deficient in providing optimized or even adequately informed design solutions. Their deficiencies relate not only to interoperability, modeling resolution and other technical aspects but also to the uncertainty of modern complex design problems (Hopfe and Hensen 2011). Furthermore, in the light of the evolving incorporation of computational design methods in

mainstream architectural practice and subsequent research focus on more advanced, adaptive and real-time performing architectural solutions this complexity is inevitably due to increase. It follows that in order for these design spaces of higher complexity to achieve an adequately higher level of performance goals, a higher level of integration of BPS tools is needed, not only in mainstream CAD software but also, and more importantly so, within the computational design frameworks that shape the forefront of performance-driven design processes.

If one adds to the design complexity the adaptability potential of the current state of the art architectural materiality, brought about by the continuously evolving fabrication methods, rapidly advancing robotics integration and forthcoming smart materials adaptation, the subsequent need for BPS integration becomes even more prominent. Given the aforementioned deficiency of the currently available BPS tools to inform optimized design solutions, it is evident that there is a need not only for further development and integration of BPS tools, especially so in computational design systems, but also the re-evaluation and re-development of current methodologies of performance-driven design to accommodate this novel, adaptable materiality.

Under this scope, this ESR project is focusing on developing an integrated performance-driven design methodology for designing with adaptive material systems. The focus of the ESR is primarily on the development of a design methodology and the respective development or interface of appropriate simulation tools that can support the design of an adaptive material system and secondarily on the development of material programming and fabrication methods to support the proposed methodology. With regards to its

performance goals, the project's primary focus is on air flow related problems and consequently the integration of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations in design. The integration of CFD in architectural computational design systems is largely unexplored, despite its significance in many environmental aspects of design. Taking into consideration the previously mentioned adaptability potential of forthcoming material systems within the context of air flow related aspects of design this integration is a key step to enabling the design of advanced responsive material systems, such as, for example, adaptable breathing skins.

This enquiry entails a number of more specific research questions. Firstly, the potential of the currently available BPS tools in relation not only to the mentioned simulation complexity challenges but also to their accessibility and usability by designers. Secondly, their ability to predict the non-static performance of adaptive materials, thus developing feedback loops between the simulation interfaces

and the design frameworks. And lastly, a question regarding the simulation resolution and the achievable level of abstraction and consequent accuracy and design exploration trade-off, which also entails the use of machine learning and other artificial intelligence methods for performance prediction.

At its current stage the project is reviewing the CFD frameworks that are currently available and integrated in computational design platforms, both at a theoretical level, through a review of the background literature as well as at a practical level through the evaluation of currently available tools in a number of student case studies within the academic environment of the ESR. This review has already demonstrated the limited capabilities and limitations of integrated CFD simulation tools and supports the need for further development of such interfaces.

The project's strategic collaboration with McNeel (Software Engineering, Spain) through a four-months secondment situated in the beginning of its second year is expected to provide an important further step for the development and integration of a CFD simulation framework within the most widely used computational design framework (i.e. Grasshopper). In order to assess the methodological hypotheses that arise from these questions it is evident that a series of case studies need to be designed, implemented and evaluated. The collaboration with Foster + Partners (Design Consultant, UK) is also expected to provide, at a later stage, a test bed for experimentation with the proposed design methodology, in order to evaluate its potential in a high-end demanding design environment.

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Hopfe, C. and Hensen, J.L.M. 2011 "Uncertainty analysis in building performance simulation for design support", *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 43, Issue 10, October 2011, Pages 2798-2805

MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMISATION IN EARLY DESIGN PHASE

ZEYNEP AKSÖZ

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THE RESEARCH

Multiple criteria optimization is a highly integrated problem solving process in the engineering practices, where the common use of these base on finding one optimal solution for a certain design problem. Recently optimization is mainly used rather in later stages of design development, where previously selected design solutions are optimized for certain predefined goals. For this reason, these methods search for a single solution that can address a steady design problem in the later phases of design.

This research project argues that the integration of multiple criteria search methodologies in the early phases of design have a large potential in expanding the scope of design space. However, in spite of design constraints, design parameters and objectives tend to remain uncertain and shifting in these earlier phases. Therefore, the early design phase can be seen as a search for the objectives and parameters within the given constraints of the design brief. Accordingly, such a phase needs a strategy that aims to investigate the design space extensively. It should inform the designer on the importance or relevance of certain design parameters and objectives for the design goal rather than finding one best solution for a single problem.

As a result, the ESR research project concentrates on discovery of a larger design space by human machine interaction where both parts are involved creatively in the process, rather than finding optimal solutions for a certain design problem. Consequently, the designer becomes the creator of a system of smaller entities and their topological interactions where the computer becomes an extension of the human mind which takes over the design search part by controlling the interactions between entities.

This collaborative design strategy brings a new perspective into design thinking. Rather than using a top down strategy, where the designer searches for the preferred solution manually and optimizing the selected solution in a later step, s/he becomes the builder of the process, investigating the topological relations between the parameters and objectives. The design solutions then will emerge by the computer's involvement using the design variables in different combinations iteratively providing an evaluation of each solution regarding the objective values. This way computer's role changes from being a problem solver or a decisive party into a suggestive collaborator, providing the designer with an overview on multiple solutions. The decision making remains in the hands of the designer, weighing and comparing the benefits of different solutions.

This method can be compared to the theory of emergence, which suggests that the certain behavioral patterns of larger systems are triggered by the interaction of the smaller and simpler components within. Looking into the design process from the perspective of emergence, the parameters become the components of the system that compose different solutions by interacting with each other. The interactions between parameters will influence the overall behavior of the system. The overall behavior can be then evaluated by understanding the relation between the parameters and objectives.

Inputs

Neighborhood relation of each cell

Grid parameters

Objectives

Outputs

Plot coverage and morphology

max 40 floors

min 3 floors
Building Height

The research project uses this emergent behavior as a strategy to investigate the design space, that combines human intention with computer's processing power and lack of intention to visit different solutions and evaluate these. In order to develop such method, the existing multiple criteria search methods such as genetic algorithms, evolutionary programming and simulated annealing are being

reviewed and evaluated according to performance, convergence time and the diversity by using optimization benchmark problems such as hill climber or travelling salesman problem. Additionally, new decision making strategies developed in the field of robotics, such as artificial neural networks, are being investigated and being combined with the previously mentioned methods and evaluated equally.

Though design problems are by nature different than optimization benchmark problems, which evaluate the method by comparing the convergence time and systems ability to find multiple global optima. In order to understand the applicability of these methods in design problems, the methods should be carried over to design based experiments, where the parameters and objectives become much more complex. Here, the description of the design problem is crucial in the evaluation of applicability of these methods for design. Therefore, the research highly focuses on the parametrization methods and design of experiments in architectural and structural scale, comparing the description of design problems in both disciplines. For this reason, the involvement of the industry partners is of a high importance. There is an intense collaboration with the structural engineering office structure in Stuttgart also architectural office BIG Copenhagen. The interdisciplinary partnership provides two different point of views for design. Accordingly, the experiments are conducted in different scales and later these different scale of experiments will be evaluated according to similarities or differences in setting of the problems and the design of the experiments.

ALTERNATE MEANS TO COMMUNICATE MEASURE

DIMITRIE STEFANESCU

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THE RESEARCH

The research focuses on how complex simulation based design can be collated and communicated internally (within a design team) and externally (various expert systems/stakeholder groups).

Communication is an essential activity that permeates the design industry in all its aspects, from ideation to materialisation - from the drawing board to the shop floor. The contemporary context involves a growing number of stakeholders from various backgrounds that, through their interaction, enable the definition and subsequent solving of design problems and assignments.

Architecture, as a discipline, has given birth to various other expert systems in order to meet its goals and match its own ambitions and those of the context it serves. Tracing the history of design, one can remark that it has followed a trend of speciation characteristic to the modern age. From the centralised role of "master builder" in complete control of all aspects of design, from ideation to materialisation, the architect is now just one of the many stakeholders involved in the design process. In other words, the designer's privileged position in coordinating the production of the built environment has devolved into a subsidiary role surrounded by regulatory bodies, construction managers as well as private funding

bodies.

Design questions are not simple, “linear” or “tame” - they can not be solved a classical approach of data gathering, analysis, solution formulation and implementation. Most assignments share the characteristics of “wick-ed” problems: open ended questions that can be understood only after the formulation of a solution. Moreover, they have no clear right or wrong answers: multiple stakeholders have vested interests in the issue at hand and as such are (self-)entitled to judge the solutions.

The main dilemmas associated with a pluralist and socially complex design environment revolve around the difficulty in countering the fragmentation forces that are invariably attacking any project of sufficient complexity. Creating coherence amounts to fostering shared understanding and shared commitment amongst the involved parties. While shared shared commitment is largely dependent on social skills and other factors, shared understanding can be encouraged through transparency: revealing the inner workings of the stakeholder’s group values and inter-relating them into a coherent system.

The intention is to situate the research - at least intellectually - at an abstract level that does not limit itself to the specificities of one particular design assignment or stakeholder group. Information is continuously ex-changed between human and non-human actors during all the stages of the design process - from early conceptualisation, through various simulations (structural, financial, environmental, etc.) to fabrication, assembly and realisation. Consequently, the central investigative position is occupied by the effective new ways in which we can now transform & transmit information due to the affordances of the digital medium in general, and those of contemporary computational design tools in particular. Summing up, developing and enabling a methodological approach through which digital parametric models can be used as conduits for a transparent & engaging process of collaborative problem

definition and value creation in the production of the built environment is the main ambition of this research project. It is our hope that our contribution will be relevant for the defragmentation of contemporary projects' dynamics.

Towards this end, an open source design data communication platform (Speckle) is being developed. It is un-opinionated and operates at an abstract level by facilitating the sharing of the essential building blocks that comprise the alphabet of design (geometry and textual/numeric information). It allows for the interactive exploration of solution spaces - defined by input parameters and performance measures - through the simultaneous comparison of all possible solutions. It already is in active use by >500 content creators (designers) and >10000 content consumers, and has been used in the V&A exhibition "Engineering the World: Ove Arup and the Philosophy of Total Design".

The Research

Simulation for design

Current methods for simulation assume single scale engagement across separate phases and exclude the simulation of material and fabrication processes. Recent research identifies new opportunities for simulation to link the design of material with the design of structures. This creates new implications for material deployment that necessitate new methods for analysing, specifying and controlling fabrication.

The topic is tackled in the innochain Workpackage 4, which will examine how simulation can be used as a means to cross between scales and synthesise material performances with machine-driven processes.

The Workpackage is lead by the KTH School of Architecture.

MULTI-SCALAR MODELLING FOR FREE-FORM TIMBER STRUCTURES

PAUL POINET

THE RESEARCH | 8

ESR NUMBER: ESR06

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold & Design to
Production

INSTITUTE: CITA

The PhD research investigates a new conceptual and computational framework that employs Multi-Scalar Modelling techniques in order to overcome the problem of big data management and to enable a more integrative digital workflow during the geometrical discretization of spatial structures.

Taking the design probe of free-form structures composed of glue-laminated timber beams, the present research is developed in close collaboration with two industry partners of the InnoChain ETN network: designtoproduction (design consultant, CH) and Buro Happold (engineering office, GB). Part of the “Simulating Design” work package, the project focuses on the implementation of Multi-Scalar Modelling concepts and techniques as a means to work within a continuous design environment in which an abstract network of glue-laminated timber beams is iteratively updated through geometrical and structural optimizations at different levels of resolution.

A particular focus lies in the segmentation strategy of the overall timber structure that depends on structural requirements and the different types of constraints related to fabrication, transportation and assembly. Where current working practices decouple

segmentation processes within a discrete digital workflow, this research aims to integrate and negotiate the different parameters that drive the same segmentation strategy within a continuous environment. Such a process could (re-)unify the fragmented information space of a complex architectural project through the linkage of parallel design frameworks in which models with differentiated objectives can interact between themselves through different scales and resolutions.

The present design probe uses the process of abstracting complex geometries into abstract networks which serves as a point of departure for setting up a Multi-Scalar Modelling environment for free-form timber structures. Two-dimensional networks can be easily analyzed and manipulated using graph theory, which allows the establishment of connections between nodes through edges. Specific related algorithms enable the user to navigate within a graph, access and manipulate its particular data sets (dividing a graph into subgraphs, checking the number of connections at each node, asking for all the existing closed polygons within it, etc.). Graph theory is seen here as the core concept of parametric/associative modelling. Generative Components, CATIA or the Grasshopper environment are all based on directed acyclic constraint graphs (or data-tree structures) that enable the user to specify dependencies between objects. However, the focus in these modelling strategies lies only on the creation of geometry and therefore the graphs themselves and their inherent hierarchies are generally not (or not enough) considered. Thus, traceability between parents and children is often difficult to keep along the continuous modelling actions of the user.

At CITA (Centre for Information Technology and Architecture), the interest in graphs and data-tree structures as methods of modelling and representation has informed different architectural design research projects in order to obtain a better understanding of the relationships between the different structural elements and to ease afterwards the fabrication process. The research project *The Tower* (Deleuran et al. [1]) features a modelling environment that allows the user to directly interact with simulated bending active glass fiber rods that are continuously aggregated and activated by additional strings. When changes occur, a graph is constantly (re-) generated and displays the current assembly logic between all the

objects. For the conception process of the Stressed-Skins prototype (Nicholas et al. [2]), traceability features have been implemented through adaptive meshing techniques, which allowed the direct transfer of information – from the manipulation of the global design at a macro scale to the calculation of forming strains and material thinning at a micro scale. This particular design framework also allows retroactive feedback – or bi-directional information flows – from high resolution simulations to the global design (and vice versa). In this case, the vertical integration of design and fabrication through directed acyclic graphs is replaced by an interactive and horizontal integration of the design process itself where nodes can communicate and exchange back and forth between each other. In the present research, graphs are used to map the specific dependencies between objects existing in free-form timber structures.

Taking as starting points the digital workflow existing within the practice of DesignToProduction and the specific modelling strategies developed at Buro Happold for the negotiation of multiple constraints constraints, the PhD research investigates on the modelling of a continuous hierarchy defined across scales within a graph (from an abstract network of lines to the complete fabrication data set of each architectural component).

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SIMULATING ANISOTROPIC MATERIAL

CHRISTOPH HERMANN

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THE RESEARCH

ESR NUMBER: ESR07

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Cloud9 & Blumer
Lehmann

INSTITUTE: IoA

In Material Science, anisotropy is the directional dependence of a material's physical property – unlike isotropy, in which a material's properties are identical in all directions. The recent separation of digital design processes into modelling, analysis and fabrication has led to the predominance of geometry as the main driver of form-generation. This results in a conventional way of assigning materials during fabrication and production. Anisotropy conditions can be found in the grain structure of wood or in the fibre orientation of composites, and can act as an interesting material optimization model within the design process. Finite Element Method (FEM) software used in sophisticated structural engineering packages provides dependable anisotropic simulation; however, these are computationally heavy and do not deal with complex geometries efficiently. Even though advances now permit lightweight structural assessment to be carried out at the beginning of the design process current practice does not take full advantage of anisotropic material properties. This research intends to develop intuitive lightweight parametric models to use a material's anisotropy as a medium for structural optimization and form-generation. Parallels are drawn on principles found in nature where physical matter is programmed by

factors that include structural and mechanical efficiency as well as reaction to environmental conditions.

It is speculated that the phenomenon of anisotropy can be incorporated as a design strategy used as an approach for digital form-finding. Can anisotropic material conditions be used as a means of structural optimization at the early design stage? Which workflows can be established by interlinking and modifying contemporary, state-of-the-art design tools of various parallel fields to create intuitive, practice oriented and high-performance modelling aids for anisotropic simulation? At which points in a design chain can those tools be used to enhance or replace the common practice of choosing a standard material?

At the projects current stage an integrated and unobstructed lightweight structural optimization model has been developed within the Grasshopper platform using third party add-ons, as well as a number of custom-coded add-ons. These Grasshopper add-ons are written in programming language C#. As an example, in the field of computer graphics, fast algorithms have been developed to evenly place curves that are tangent to the velocity of a flow field. This allows for expressing elegantly complex flow visualizations. It is mandatory to use customized code to incorporate this or similar methods within Grasshopper3d to interactively control density, scale, flow and articulation of the anisotropy. The parametric model now forms the foundation for the ongoing digital experimentation period of digital simulation, experimentation and optimization. Also alternative methods to simulate anisotropy as means of form-finding are investigated by using Kangaroo2 to define simulation goals via custom codes goals and loops. While this method is not necessarily accurate it is extremely fast and allows as high degree of interaction. Currently the research investigates options to combine Kangaroo with Karamba3D to step wise analyse the

physical simulation. This period will result in catalogue of case studies showcasing the potential of simulating and/or designing anisotropic material in the design stage. The case studies will evaluate anisotropy as a means of structural optimization, as well as form generation. Furthermore, they will form the basis of the manufacture of physical prototypes to create a re-informing loop between the digital model and the behaviour of the physical samples.

Once case studies conducted in the digital experimentation phase show promising performance, a parallel phase to manufacture prototypes will be initiated. Various studies exploring the

relationship of anisotropic properties between real world prototypes and the digital model will be carried out. Deviations between the digital model and the behaviour of the physical samples will be investigated to feedback to the digital design process. Prototypes will explore the anisotropic qualities of wood. Therefore, it is expected that a series of physical prototypes will be produced with the industry partner Blumer Lehmann. It is paramount that Blumer Lehmann play an active role during this period. As an interdisciplinary architectural practice located in Barcelona, Cloud 9, are working at the interface between architecture and art, digital processes and the development of technological materials. As Cloud 9 is committed to embracing new technological developments and performative dimensions of architecture it will become a great source of knowledge and exchange. Multiple collaboration frameworks will be feasible. Within the collaboration, Cloud 9's previous projects will be explored to evaluate potential opportunities to integrate this research in upcoming projects. The integration within ongoing real-life projects will be a form of collaborative enquiry worth actively pursuing. Additionally, it will be central to form a connected relationship to exchange knowledge and expertise. Cloud 9 will be an important partner to rely on and to evaluate relevance of the research within industry.

VIRTUAL PROTOTYPING FRP

JAMES SOLLY

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THE RESEARCH

ESR NUMBER: ESR08

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: S-form & Foster
+ Partners

INSTITUTE: ITKE

Digital fabrication technology offers the possibility to widen the range of processes available through standardised fabrication and bypass limitations on the fabrication of bespoke forms. Often accompanied by trial-and-error approaches, the limits of digital fabrication methods are quickly reached without a thorough understanding of material properties and forming processes. Virtual prototyping replaces material prototyping by simulating the fabrication processes: machining, material interaction and forming in order to test and evaluate material performance both during and after fabrication.

The research aim of ESR08 is to apply a virtual prototyping methodology to the Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) fabrication process "Coreless Filament Winding" (CFW), a novel addition to the set of Advanced/Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) technologies. Since 2012 the ITKE and ICD have actively developed the CFW process, utilising industrial robotic systems. Continuous carbon and glass-fibre rovings are wound around minimal structural frameworks at the boundaries of the proposed geometry, using the precision of the robotic tools to ensure they are passed accurately around closely-spaced winding points. The free interaction of the

fibres within the fabrication space creates then creates the final geometry without a mould.

The CFW method has been successfully used for the ICD/ITKE Research Pavilions of 2012 and 2013/2014, the University of Stuttgart Hannover Fair Stand 2015 and the new 2016 Elytra Filament Pavilion.

Currently, the development of suitable bounding-frame geometry and winding syntax (the sequence of fibre additions around the bounding frame) is reliant upon handmade models and the experience of the designer (often also developed through models and previous projects). This has been found to be effective, but in many cases the early 1:1 prototypes reveal issues that were not uncovered in the modelling stage.

Thus the ESR08 research proposes to focus on the simulation of fibre position during the winding stage and to develop tools that enable a virtual prototypes to replace physical prototypes, supporting designers and increasing the speed of design iteration whilst reducing material waste.

Initial work completed to date may be grouped into key areas as

outlined below:

THE ELYTRA PAVILION:

Since the commencement of the research in September 2015, most time has been spent on creating the Elytra Pavilion, recently installed at the V&A Museum in London. The design and fabrication of this pavilion has continued development of the CFW technique to deliver a semi-permanent FRP canopy structure that incorporates

a polycarbonate cladding layer. The project was delivered by a combined team from the ITKE and ICD at the University of Stuttgart. My role within this team (along with my colleague Valentin Koslowski, ITKE) focussed on structural simulation and material/component testing. Structural simulation was used to determine component differentiation through a two-stage shape and size optimisation process that provided the dimension and reinforcement data required for fabrication.

In order for the simulation of this highly non-linear structure to be accurate we performed a series of small-scale material tests as well as full-scale component tests in order to provide the correct properties for finite element analysis.

Our team designed every detail for the pavilion including custom connection systems between the FRP elements and the ETFE core enclosure, polycarbonate covering, steel supports and foundation system.

Apart from the composite element of the pavilion my work included developing the anchorage details (the pavilion is so light that wind could lift it up) and other interfaces with the existing V&A built fabric. This included on-site ground testing and the full setting-out of the pavilion within the space.

The Elytra Filament Pavilion project has given further validity to the CFW fabrication process as a method to create performative composite structures and thus provided a profound starting position for further development of the technology in the ESR08 research.

SIMULATION OF FIBRE WINDING

Current industrial FRP process simulation software is aimed at the simulation of winding onto a solid mandrill and thus the simulations are more focussed on the testing how to arrange fibres onto that pre-defined geometry. Thus form and fibre arrangements are

(largely) decoupled. The fibre simulations are typically performed in one of two ways; simple mathematical rules based on surface curvature or non-linear finite element analysis with discrete contact elements. These FEA models in particular are numerically complex, requiring significant computational power and run-time.

With coreless fibre winding, the formable geometries are inherently linked to fibre syntax through the Fibre-Fibre interaction that occurs within the working space. Thus a designer looking to utilise this process must either fully understand the process or have access to tools that provide guidance on design possibilities.

A lightweight, high-speed process simulation tool is currently under development in collaboration with other researchers at the University of Stuttgart. The aim of this tool is to directly simulate a proposed series of fibre placement steps, looking for issues in fibre-

fibre contact and created geometry whilst also checking the range of internal fibre stresses during processing. Work on this tool was progressed, in part, during the Innochain Workshop 1.2 “Simulation for Design” held at the University of Stuttgart.

INDUSTRY PARTNER ENGAGEMENT

In these early stages of research, discussions with both industry partners (Foster + Partners and S-Form) have been held to understand the relevance of the proposed research within their fields and to determine where they might input back into the research.

With S-Form, their encyclopaedic knowledge of FRP materials has led to several relevant discussions and ideas for how CFW might be utilised to provide some process improvement within current FRP products.

Discussions with the Specialist Modelling Group (SMG) at Foster + Partners have focussed more on the relevance of FRP in architecture and the particular challenges that are posed in this context compared to uses of FRP in other fields (such as aerospace).

Discussions on material relevance have led to a critical review of the benefits of FRP in current construction and the need for a clear explanation of this at concept design, else these inherent opportunities may be lost at the interfaces of different structural systems and materials. It is proposed that a paper considering the state of the art in Composite Architecture should be prepared.

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SIMULATING CONCRETE FORMWORK

VASILY SITNIKOV

120

THE RESEARCH |

ESR NUMBER: ESR09

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Buro Happold

INSTITUTE: KTH

The present research attempts to integrate means of computation in design and fabrication processes of architectural constructions of reinforced concrete. The research domain is outlined by two extremes of the design discipline – the digital and the material. By testing various strategies of bridging the transition from digital modelling to industrial fabrication, the research aspires to establish an efficient workflow of a design and fabrication method of freeform structures of concrete. Digital software, material systems, and design routes that link the former two are here to provide a fertile field for interdisciplinary innovations for technology of concrete casting.

The workflow development begins with a definition of the digital input that is generally considered to be a digital simulation of a physical system. The ability to simulate a dynamic interaction of physical forces, to model material behavior, and therefor to generate mass of design relevant digital data out of a abstract preconditions has a potential to seriously improve structural, ecological end economic performance of a design product. By attributing physical properties like mass and stiffness to a digital

3D model and by exposing it to an external dynamic forces, architectural design methodology undergoes significant changes. In conditions when structural task requires new levels of plasticity, the process of advanced digital prototyping can help to minimize usage and waste of material as well as to optimize the process of fabrication, reducing the amount of embedded energy, and thus carbon footprint of the final product. On the other hand the new design environment enables real time digital prototyping of any constructive types and allows designer to estimate structural validity on the very early design stages. Such a fusion of aesthetic and structural criteria represents a new modality of the design process, evoking a notion of design methodology with an embedded optimization.

In the research frameworks an ultimate example of a generative tool that incorporates simulation considered to be the method of topology optimization simulation. It is a mathematical model of solving structural problems, prioritizing minimal use of a given material. A structural problem is mediated through a set of vectors representing loads, physical properties of the material, and a set of performance targets. Therefore topology optimization allows to retrieve the most rational distribution of material in space from a set of formal requirements. Development of this computational tool can drastically improve quality of concrete constructions, providing best-fitting design to every configuration of a structural problem.

In collaboration with engineers from Buro Happold, the subjects of structural optimizations in concrete constructions is being further examined and elaborated to provide an intuitive control over form generated through topology optimization.

However optimized topology meets serious obstacles on the stage of full scale materialization. Fabrication of complex free-form double curved objects of reinforced concrete in conventional industry requires a very complex formwork, thus a laborious, time consuming, and wasteful construction process. This research therefore attempts to develop a specific concrete formwork system to meet the necessary degree of geometrical complexity on rational costs of production. The design environment generated by anchoring research mere to a certain geometrical topology, provides a wide specter for speculations about possible design routes. By altering methods of algorithmic interpretations and geometrical representations of the input topology and through a revision of the very fundamental principles of concrete casting a novel design routes can be discovered. From this derives the main objective of the research that is to propose a robust and simple chain of procedure to ease the transition from digital design to its material embodiment in concrete industry, establishing a soft type of formwork.

SIMULATING ROBOTIC FEEDBACK

GIULIO BRUGNARO

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THE RESEARCH |

ESR NUMBER: ESR10

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: BIG & ROK

INSTITUTE: BSA

The research focuses on the development of robotic fabrication methods for architectural production that aim to bring the explorative dimension of the design process into the fabrication stage, thanks to an intuitive and accessible interface through which the designer could actively engage with the potential of material behaviours and specific manufacturing techniques.

The overall process is not devised as a linear progression from a prescribed design to its materialisation but rather as a flexible and adaptive framework to drive robotic fabrication processes where the design moment unfolds together with the fabrication one, constantly being informed by real-time sensor data acquired through feedback loops.

In this perspective, simulation is not used as a predictive tool to project assumptions from the digital to the physical world but the other way around to compile the incoming stream of sensor information into an updating digital environment that allows the designer to maintain the control over the fabrication process and intervene at any time to adjust it.

Feedback information is not only necessary to perform a specific fabrication task and validate the simulation but could be collected

into larger datasets of fabrication parameters, material behaviours and design strategies, which allow the system to become a learning and evolving tool that could adapt and improve over time based on previous experience.

Furthermore, while programming a robot could be time-consuming and it requires a considerable amount of expertise, the recorded information could be used to train the machine toward the desired outcome rather than explicitly instructing it line-by-line. From this point of view, recording the totality of gestures, and related fabrication parameters, of a craftsman carving several wood pieces,

represents an opportunity to capture, at least partially, the richness of the tacit knowledge acquired through years of experience and translate it to an automated fabrication environment.

Challenging current CNC machining techniques, unable to work with the richness of heterogeneous material, such as timber, or rapidly adapt and improve after each iteration according to different fabrication tasks as it happens in traditional human craftworks, the research is specifically focusing on subtractive manufacturing techniques. These are approached from two different perspective, high-level information about the overall cutting strategies and execution of a design intention, and low-level, specifically related to material behaviours, tools and local manipulation techniques.

Ultimately, the learning and feedback-driven framework represents a tool to foster an active collaboration between the human and the machine. The designer operates within a system that is flexible and able to receive feedback, not only about fabrication parameters or materials, but also from its human counterpart. In this way, the artefact being produced is the unique result of this interaction and would not have been possible with only one of the two parts alone.

The research is enhanced through a strategic collaboration with two leading design firms such as ROK Office (Zurich, CH) and BIG (Copenhagen, DK). The main idea is to bring the overall design and robotic fabrication framework devised in the research and apply it to a specific architectural scenario/commission, in order to test it in a real-world setting and developing it within a professional context. The possible outcome would be a small scale project, either an interior design or a pavilion that showcase the potential of these novel production methods within an architectural context.

The Research

Materialising design

Current methods for materialisation within the building industry are based on mass production. They rely on the standardisation of material and fabrication to afford control and optimise material use. With digitisation these methods become outdated and new models for material optimisation emerge. Where subtractive digital fabrication techniques have matured and been applied to realise complex buildings, recent research efforts utilise bespoke machines or industrial robots as general fabrication tools for additive fabrication to innovate mass customised materials with designed performances.

The topic is tackled in the innochain Work package 5 , which will focus on trialling fabrication and planning methods for new designed materials that embed material optimisation within their composition.

The workpackage is lead by the The Bartlett School of Architecture / University College London

CONCRETE PRINTING

HELENA WESTERLIND

The introduction of additive manufacturing technology in concrete construction challenges several of the principles that currently condition the use of concrete within the built environment; such as the dependence upon formwork and the tendency for prefabrication and standardization of architectural elements. This PhD research, pursues controlled deposition of concrete at the intersection between material science and architecture, in search of newfound correspondences between materiality, form and fabrication.

The practice of placing concrete by deposition signifies a fundamental departure from traditional techniques of forming through casting. A shift emphasised by the fact that the formalisation of concrete-flow is no longer determined by the restraint and control provided by the opposing force of a formwork, but by self-organising and self-supporting capacities of the material itself. The scope of the project is particularly concerned with this inverted shift in concrete performance; both in terms of practical implications for the design of the concrete mix and its associated rheological behaviour, and in relation to the new material processes

involved in the actualisation of form. For this purpose, the control offered by robotic deposition is used as a mode of investigating material flow and the internal resistance to deformation caused by forces at molecular level in response to various external forces acting upon the material. By turning attention to the behaviour of the material itself, and to the articulation of material flow, the project seeks to contribute to an understanding of concrete as active matter and to explore its inherent potential in relation architecture's theoretical underpinnings.

The use of additive manufacturing in architectural production generally adhere to linear workflows in which a predetermined geometry is turned into a physical object, through a process of layered material deposition. The popular use of the term "3D printing", and the notion of the term "resolution" as a measure to indicate how accurately a physical object corresponds to the geometry of its digital counterpart, highlight a culture of making that clearly follows a hylomorphic tradition that considers form to be imposed on passive matter in order to give it structure. Within the emerging field of 3D printing concrete, this project represents a trajectory that pursues a material approach, for which the term "3D printing" is held highly insufficient.

After a period of material investigation, the project will develop by exploring bi-directional workflows and feedback mechanisms with the aim of establishing a continuous dialogue between material behaviour and design intent. The notion of "material resolution", as opposed to "geometric resolution", will be central to the work as it emphasises the ability to synthesise internal and external forces involved in the process of deposition for the purpose of optimizing concrete performance.

MATERIAL GRADIENT FRP

SAMAN SAFFARIAN

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THE RESEARCH

Building envelopes not only mediate between exterior climatic conditions and interior comfort requirements, but are also fully charged with potentials to represent cultural, social and political aspects of society. A vivid manifestation of this is the constant transformation, mutation and evolution of Architectural styles, and the artistic, stylistic and compositional means through which various ideologies in different societies are conveyed. In summary, building facades are required to fulfill technical and representational requirements simultaneously. The methodology of this research project will be informed by this duality.

Current trends in non-kinetic facade design, such as double-skin systems, provide little room for further technical development that can enhance energy performance. However recent research and experiments have showcased that responsive and adaptive façade systems have the potential to further reduce energy consumption, due to their ability to constantly change their geometry to best fit the performance criteria of the overall building at any given moment. However, built examples of kinetic facades have so far heavily relied on rigid body mechanics to achieve movement.

These complex mechanical systems are mostly guided along straight translation or rotation axis, resulting not only in geometrical constraints, but also mechanical complexity. These systems are expensive to manufacture, prone to failure, hard to maintain and therefore often not feasible in terms of operation economy.

Recent biomimetic research on movements found in biology has identified strategies to achieve mobility by utilizing elastic deformation of fibrous materials to drive transformation. Kinetic elastic systems (compliant mechanisms) represent a valid alternative to rigid mechanisms for climate adaptive building envelopes and have the potential to dramatically reduce the mechanical complexity of kinetic elements while providing a wide range of complex yet efficient movements that are arguably more suitable for the design of freeform architectural envelopes, can operate more economically and are more resilient to environmental impact. Focusing on Fibre Reinforced Polymers, strategies for varying material stiffness will be investigated through precise fibre deployment and specific lay-up patterns, in order to fabricate elastic kinetic systems with optimized movement efficiency and reduced mechanical complexity.

Although the design of these kinetic systems is mainly informed and driven by quantifiable performance criteria such as fabrication feasibility, operation economy and energy efficiency, there exists a number of not-readily-quantifiable, yet equally important factors that need to be taken into account at early design stages. These include psychological and physiological effects of such systems on building occupants, methods of user control and levels of interaction and last but not least the novel palette of design opportunities that these kinetic structures inherently provide. This research aims to establish design guidelines for kinetic façade systems that correspond to the requisite criteria for material

performance, provide occupant comfort and are choreographed to adequately fulfill representational role of building envelopes in architectural terms.

APPLIED ROBOTICS – CONTROLLED MATERIAL DEPOSITION

ARTHUR PRIOR

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THE RESEARCH |

ESR NUMBER: ESR13

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Foster + Partners & Buro Happold

INSTITUTE: BSA

This project investigates robotic fabrication strategies that combine additive and subtractive manufacturing. Its goal is to generate novel prototyping workflows. The project targets three areas of research: Industrial Styling Clay - a wax-based material native to the automotive industry for prototyping vehicles at a 1:1 scale - is investigated as a viable medium for Fused Deposition Modelling; Multi-axis tool-path strategies are developed, capitalising on the affordances of robotic fabrication environments with six degrees of freedom and therefore unlocking the geometric constraints of traditional cartesian additive systems; Hybrid additive-subtractive fabrication workflows are explored, prefiguring a best-of-both-worlds scenario that combines the attributes of each method.

Styling Clay for Fused Deposition Modelling

While being composed of one of the most abundant naturally-occurring materials - clay - Industrial Styling Clay came into being in the late 19th Century as an admixture of clay, oils and waxes. Since the 1920's it has been used in the automotive industry for prototyping vehicles at a 1:1 scale. This practice has evolved alongside computational design methodologies and remains the most

important means of evolving and evaluating new designs. As a phase-change material, Styling Clay exhibits potential for Fused Deposition Modelling and more-over has properties lending to excellent machinability. A significant aspect of this project is concerned with developing tooling for accurately dosing this highly viscous, phase-change material.

What can Multi-Axis Motion Control offer Additive Manufacturing? Traditional Additive Manufacturing systems are bound by cartesian coordinate systems with three axes of motion. This underlying constraint limits the potential breadth of tool-path strategies to 'Constant Height Slicing', which yields a number of undesirable

artefacts and impedes part complexity. This project develops alternative tool-path strategies based on geodesics - a mode of representing objects in which geodesic lines (arcs) replace the straight lines of planar geometry. These geodesic tool-paths are intended to be executed by industrial robots, therefore capitalising on the affordances of these machines that are characterised by

multi-degree of freedom kinematic chains.

Hybrid Fabrication Strategies: Can Additive and Subtractive Manufacturing Coact?

Additive and Subtractive Manufacturing are often presented as opposing methods, each with their own benefits and drawbacks. This project aims to develop a fabrication method that can support both Fused Deposition Modelling and Milling in optimal proportions as needed. As such, the geometric freedom of additive manufacturing, its economic use of materials and the precision and surface finish of machining are harnessed as part of an integrated, flexible prototyping workflow. As essentially generic tools, industrial robots are well suited to performing a number of different functions within the same cell.

This research project is conducted primarily through practical experimentation at The Bartlett School of Architecture's workshop and robotics laboratory: B-MADE. InnoChain ETN network industrial partners Buro Happold and Foster + Partners contribute their expertise in the respective fields of Architectural Design and Engineering, both with a particular focus on complex geometry. As companies renowned for delivering bespoke architectural and design solutions, prototyping forms an inherent aspect of every project undertaken.

DESIGN FOR MANUFACTURE AND ASSEMBLY - INTEGRATED ASSEMBLY ANALYSIS IN NONLINEAR TIMBER CONSTRUCTION

KASPER AX

ESR NUMBER: ESR14

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Design to Production
& Blumer Lehmann

INSTITUTE: CITA

With a core focus on wood joinery, this project investigates how architects and engineers can integrate the planning of manufacturing and assembly procedures into a synthesized, computational design process. It argues that assembly planning remains an unassimilated part of the contemporary design process, which complicates a synchronization across the building industry. Consequently, this causes a restriction of design potentials offered by technological advancements. The project is situated within the 'Materialising Design' work package of the InnoChain ETN network and collaborates closely together with DesignToProduction (design consultant, CH) and Blumer-Lehmann (timber fabricator, CH) to develop innovative planning processes that interface new material practices with the requirements of industrial fabrication. Through several built, large scale projects, such as the Metz Pompidou Center and the Haesley Nine Bridges Gulf Club in South Korea, both industrial partners have highly qualified experience with nonlinear design and manufacture in timber construction and its impact on assembly. The collaboration with the industrial partners contextualizes the project in an industrially relevant setting, and establishes a holistic understanding of issues related to manufacture

Sequence Player - interlocking frame

01 Elements 1-10

02 Elements 11-20

03 Elements 21-30

04 Elements 31-40

05 Elements 41-50

and assembly in the timber construction industry. Integrated assembly analysis: Contemporary workflows across the building industry are typically incorporating multiple computational models that enable a high level of complexity and precision, through dynamic data-flows between the various stages of the building process. The transfer of data between the design phases happens through an associated network of models that perform different tasks to feed information back and forth in an 'extended digital chain'. Especially in the earlier stages of a design process, from initial idea up until fabrication, various types of interfaces and simulation engines has enabled better analysis and planning possibilities for individualized design solutions. However, designers and builders often plan, evaluate and perform assembly procedures through predominantly manual approaches, that impede a higher level of complexity in nonlinear timber construction. The concept of 'integrated assembly analysis' aims to add assembly procedures

into the extended digital chain, by establishing a planning tool that enables feasibility analysis of assembly sequences in early stages of design. The project investigates the concept of assembly from two mutually depending angles, that transfer concepts from the parallel fields of mechanical engineering, computer science and product design: 'Logistic assembly planning' concerns the overall efficiency of assembling a product where the most dominant factors include cost and time. 'Geometric assembly planning' concerns the spatial interdependencies of specific elements. The project hypothesizes, that transferring assembly planning as far into the early stages of design as possible, can save significant cost and time in the overall process of building.

Although computationally aided design and fabrication has altered the possibilities within the timber construction industry during the last decade, making way for more versatile geometries and new design possibilities, the principles of the most commonly used wood joinery largely remain the same. However, with an extended access to spatial variation and geometric complexity, the functional demands of the single joint has increased. The project makes use of computationally based design and fabrication methods to examine how to imbed new types of material intelligence into the single wood joint, by feeding information from the assembly analysis into the early design stage.

By critically evaluating the reciprocal concepts of preassembly versus on site assembly, the project questions: Through an extended digital chain that enables early evaluation of assembly sequences, are we able to transfer the qualities of preassembly to the later stages of the design process and vice versa? In contemporary timber construction what is more appropriate: To design a system or to systematize a design?

SMALL SCALE ROBOTIC MANUFACTURING FOR THE LARGE SCALE BUILDINGS - PHRIENDS* FOR SHELLS

STEPHANIE CHALTIEL

ESR NUMBER: ESR15

INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS: Cloud9 & ROK

INSTITUTE: IAAC

Can new Phriends* processes involving gentle natural material projection on fabric form work allow sustainable innovative large earthen structures on site techniques to be developed?

Robots and Earth Architecture

This research is based on exploring the potential of marrying robotic fabrication with revisited principles of ancient earth architecture in the fabrication process of earthen shells. Natural material pulverization combined with fine-tuned manual craft in the fabrication of earthen shells have been explored physically since November 2015 within the Innochain research. Matter to Material

The natural material used are the typical earth construction ingredients: clay, sand, fibers, water and natural stabilizers like cellulose, olive oils etc.

The degree of viscosity, the density and size of the fibers, the water

*Phriends: We will define Phriends in this research as the safe interaction between people performing manual craft and robot spraying matter in the edification of earthen shells.

proportion need to be tested at each new project as they need to be tested on site.

Viscous and Fibrous Matter Soft Robotic projection

This research is based on a large amount of physical experimentation at scale 1/1 involving robots of about 1 m reach and through a swarm of small robots working collectively and interacting with the material system spraying the viscous and fibrous material on temporary fabric formwork.

Real Time Feedback Loops

One of the main challenges in the setting up of this new construction method based on real time feedback loops allowing

the constant re adaptation of robotically sprayed material on the light and unstable temporary large formwork. The angle, velocity, pressure, cone of spraying are part of the main variables.

Fast Monolithic Structures

The structures being developed are monolithic maintaining a goal of fast fabrication.

The temporary formworks are light, easily assembled and can be used more than one time.

The temporary formworks are maintained by bending removable rods forming the veins of the shells allowing me to define very specific geometries and morphologies of structures.

Non stable formworks

This new construction method is about taking advantage of the soft formworks reconfiguring themselves constantly under the weight of the wet earthen mixes and while the different layers dry.

Hence the exciting approach of a constant feedback loop that would consider this relentless metamorphosis of the supports.

Perfect Timings

There's no magical formula about how long we need to wait in between the different layers necessary to the shells/'s edifications. However, the different families of robotic swarms will be transmitted a set of actions to execute according to different ranges of humidity, roughness, rigidity etc

Intuition and sensible testing

Each new project of robotically sprayed earthen shells need to start with some protocols that will fine tune the maximum osmosis between small robot spraying and the right matter consistency of matter according to the different stages of construction. For example, the first layers applied on the fabric are very liquid and don't contain fibers. Once those ones are dry it is about applying viscous mixes still with no fibers but heavier and stickier. The last

layers have fibers. Some Jute fabric is also applied by strips in between the layers allowing the earthen shells to be very strong.

Patented technique and Industrial partners

The specific technique of spraying natural materials on fabric formwork through "Phriends" * interactions can be associated to Ferro cement technique but with a much higher degree of sustainability.

The idea is find an investor who is confident to bring this specific technique in a project under construction.

"Robotspraying" on ETFE panels with a swarm of small robots in network, and adapting the actions according to constant scanning and retransmitting information to robots has been discussed with Could 9 as it could fit some of their projects under construction.

The question of lost or removable formworks is still open.

Rok office in Zurich has already some precise experience in terms of robotic control applied to some architecture processes. My plan includes to fine tune with them the actions, movements, and feedback loop processes part of the "robotspraying" technique development.

The fact that robotic actions and movements are introduced in the construction world is significant and as Robotic interest is higher than construction it could be a good way to introduce the technique to a larger audience interested in innovation and an interesting way to find some clients willing to invest in innovation and sustainability.

If the patent creation works well, my career plan includes the possibility of creating a start-up company developing on site fabrication of innovative housing where the freeform geometries, and the high degree of sustainability might attract some buyers.

www.Innochain.net

